

FOREIGN BODIES OF THE ESOPHAGUS IN CHILDREN

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Target: study of the nature of foreign bodies of the esophagus in children and analysis of removal methods.

Research method. Clinical-instrumental, as well as instrumental removal of foreign bodies from the esophagus.

Research materials. Over the past 5 years, 18 children aged 9 months to 14 years have been in the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Children's Medical Center with a diagnosis of "Foreign body of the esophagus", of which 11 (61.1%) were boys, 7 (38.9%) were girls. %). When analyzing the nature of swallowed objects, organic objects accounted for 8 (44%) cases (sunflower seeds, wheat stalk, medicinal capsules, etc.), inorganic objects accounted for 10 (56%) (frequent metal and plastic objects, pen tips, coins, needles from a syringe, etc.). It should be noted that the largest number of observed patients were aged from 1 year to 4 years 14 (77.8%). The diagnosis of "Foreign body of the esophagus" in all cases was established on the first day from the onset of the disease on the basis of complaints from patients and anamnesis. These children had a history of swallowing a foreign body, after which hypersalivation appeared, some patients had vomiting, complaints of pain behind the sternum. An objective examination was characterized by a symptom of "hypersalivation", difficulty in swallowing liquid. If the foreign body is X-ray negative, then the shape and location can be clearly seen on the image. In other cases, the diagnosis "Foreign body of the esophagus" was established on the basis of complaints, anamnesis and objective examination data. When a foreign body was found in the first physiological narrowing of the esophagus, the foreign body was tried to be removed using laryngoscopy. And in other cases, it was necessary to remove the foreign body with the help of an esophagoscope. When a foreign body was found in the cardial part of the esophagus, it was necessary to push them into the stomach. In these patients, the foreign body departed naturally over the following days. Only in one case, during the removal of a star-shaped foreign body from the esophagus, there was a violation of the integrity of the esophagus, complicated by mediastinitis. After the removal of the foreign body from the esophagus, all patients were under observation, depending on the general and local status, they received a complex of intensive antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and symptomatic therapy, against which the patients recovered.

Conclusion: Thus, the timely treatment of patients to the hospital, the study of complaints and anamnesis, the correct determination of diagnostic and therapeutic tactics prevents the development of complications from the organs of the digestive tract and mediastinum, and contributes to the recovery of patients.

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